

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
California State University, Los Angeles

IMPROVING PEANUT BALL USE: A QUALITY IMPROVEMENT PROJECT

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

Jessica Marie Torrance

Doctoral Project Committee Approval:

Lucy VanOtterloo, PhD, RNC, CNS, Team Leader
Margaret Brady, PhD, RN, CPNP-PC, Team Member

May 2021

Author Note

Jessica Marie Torrance - <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8831-0235>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4796430

© 2021 Jessica Marie Torrance

ABSTRACT

Obstetric nursing practice includes pharmacological and non-pharmacological support of the laboring patient. One widely used non-pharmacological nursing intervention in labor is the placement of a peanut ball (PB) device. Although not well studied, PBs are associated with shorter labor and decreased risk of cesarean section (CS) in the users. However, there are variances in how often nurses use the PB. This quality improvement study sought to improve the utilization of the PB device by labor and delivery nurses through an educational course and poster display on the unit. The nulliparous, term, singleton, vertex (NTSV) CS rate at the project institution is currently above the national standards goal for the NTSV CS rate of 23.9% or less) set to improve patient quality of care. This CS benchmark rate is used as a standard for organizations to achieve due to the increased maternal morbidity, maternal mortality, and healthcare costs associated with CS births. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic restrictions, this project was suspended and carried out by proxy. However, virtual methods of education were produced along with other supplemental materials. A pre-and post-project PB knowledge survey, peanut ball use, labor hours, and birth outcomes were analyzed with mock data. By using mock data, the author demonstrated how actual data would be analyzed using various statistical tests appropriate for the type of data collected and how best to illustrate data (e.g., the number of PBs placed) via a control chart. Lessons learned can be used to implement and evaluate the project methodology in the future.

Keywords: peanut ball, nursing education, nursing interventions in labor, NTSV CS rate

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	vii
BACKGROUND	1
Significance.....	1
Problem Statement.....	2
Supporting Framework	3
Plan	6
Do.....	8
Study	8
Act.....	10
REVIEW OF LITERATURE	12
Overview.....	12
Peanut Ball Use and Labor Outcomes	14
Nursing Support and Labor Outcomes	16
Labor Nursing Acquired Knowledge and Skills.....	19
Conclusions.....	19
METHODS	21
Project Purpose	21
Ethical Considerations	21
Setting.....	22
Resources Needed.....	23
Participants.....	24
Data Collection Methods	24
Project Implementation.....	25
Measures/Tools.....	26
Evaluation	27
RESULTS	29
Pre-Implementation Data and Activities.....	29
Post-Implementation Data and Activities	32

DISCUSSION.....	38
Key Findings.....	38
Other Findings	40
Limitations.....	41
Biases	42
Recommendations.....	43
REFERENCES	45
APPENDIX A: Survey Informational Sheet.....	57
APPENDIX B: Project Survey	59
APPENDIX C: Class Outline for Peanut Ball Educational Video	60
APPENDIX D: Project Poster	61
APPENDIX E: Project Flow Chart.....	62
APPENDIX F: Peanut Ball Use Run Chart	63

LIST OF TABLES

<u>Table</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Characteristics of Nurses Completing Survey	29
2. Total Pre-Project Survey Questions Correct.....	30
3. Pre-Project Correct Survey Answers Correlated with Years of Nursing and Age	31
4. Pre-Project Correct Survey Answers and Nursing Degree	31
5. Two-Tailed Paired Samples <i>t</i> -test for the Difference Between Correct Survey Answers Pre- and Post-Project.....	33
6. Post-Project Correct Survey Answers and Nursing Degree	34
7. Frequencies of Incorrect and Correct Survey Answers Pre- and Post-Project	34
8. Two-Tailed Independent Samples <i>t</i> -test for Labor Hours Pre- vs. Post-Project.....	36
9. Two-Tailed Independent Samples <i>t</i> -test for Labor Hours by Provider.....	37

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>Figure</u>		<u>Page</u>
1. Plan, Do, Study Act, Cycle		5
2. Project Driver Diagram.....		6
3. Peanut Ball Project Flow Chart.....		9
4. Run Chart of Project Peanut Balls Placed Pre- and Post-Project.....		35

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I am forever grateful to the faculty, Dr. Lucy VanOtterloo, Dr. Margaret Brady, Dr. AJ Jadalla, Dr. Laura Sarff, and others along with the staff of the CSU-DNP community for all their guidance throughout my DNP journey. Additionally, thank you to my fellow student Mimi Dent for your friendship and support. Lastly, thank you to my wonderful spouse and extended family for giving me the courage to go back to school and achieve this goal. I could not have done this without you.

Background

The national cesarean section (CS) rate in the United States (US) increased from 23.5% in 1990 to 31.9% in 2018 (Martin, et al., 2019). The CS rate for low-risk pregnant women who are nulliparous, term, singleton, vertex presentation (NTSV), was 25.9% in 2018 (Martin et al., 2019). Although a potentially life-saving procedure, evidence suggests that despite the increasing number of CSs performed, there has not been a concomitant improvement in maternal or neonatal outcomes (Gregory et al., 2012). There are also public and private increased costs associated with CSs (Huynh et al., 2013). The average cost of a CS with private insurance or Medicaid is \$50,000; while vaginal births cost \$30,000 (Truven Health Analytics MarketScan Study, 2013). Given the increased maternal morbidity of CS causing hemorrhage, infection, deep vein thrombosis, and abnormal placentation in future pregnancies; national and international task forces have set objectives to decrease primary CS rates (American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists [ACOG], Society for Maternal Fetal Medicine [SMFM] & Caughey et al., 2014; Betrán et al. & World Health Organization [WHO], 2016; Lagrew et al., 2018). In 2016, the California Maternal Quality Care Collaborative (CMQCC) set the statewide benchmark of 23.9% for primary CS rate in low-risk pregnant women (Smith et al., 2016). The current annual NTSV CS rate at the project's facility is 25.1%.

Significance

Increased length of labor is the leading cause of primary CS (ACOG, SMFM, & Caughey et al., 2014). Interventions that increase labor length include labor induction and anesthesia use in labor (ACOG, SMFM, & Caughey et al., 2014; Hasegawa et al., 2013). Several non-pharmacological nursing strategies have been implemented to affect length of labor including continuous emotional support and maternal position changes (ACOG, 2019). Another nursing

intervention that is being investigated to reduce labor length is the use of a peanut shaped exercise ball during labor. The use of peanut balls (PB)s for low-risk patients in birthing units is supported by the CMQCC quality improvement program (Smith et al., 2016). PBs are successful in widening the pelvic outlet and facilitating the descent of the fetus and thought to be analogous to a physically upright position (Tussey et al., 2015). Upright positions in labor are known to be associated with decreased length of labor and risk of CS (Lawrence et al., 2013). Despite the popularized efficacy of PBs, there is limited published research on the use of the device.

The Association of Women's Health, Obstetric and Neonatal Nurses (AWHONN) has identified the merit of nursing education, nursing support in labor, and use of nursing interventions in reducing primary CS rates and the subsequent impact on patient outcomes and experiences (AWHONN, 2018; Burke, 2013). In a study by Bell et al. (2017) nursing education provided on PB use as part of an intrapartum protocol to manage labor in nulliparous patients demonstrated a significant increase in the use of PBs and a decreased rate of CS across three hospital settings post instruction. Furthermore, nurses were observed to be highly receptive to initiating non-pharmacological interventions and tools in labor after receiving training on assessing labor pain and directed treatments (Roberts et al., 2010).

Problem Statement

At the project facility, the annual NTSV CS rate is 25.1%. This institution has attempted to decrease the CS rate through various efforts including incorporating the use of PB devices during labor. However, the project author noted inconsistent utilization of the PB device in the intrapartum setting. In addition, although a PB is available for each laboring patient, according to nursing administration, the obstetric nursing staff at this facility did not receive formal PB instruction and training. Therefore, considering the importance of reducing the CS rate of low-

risk women and to improve overall maternal birth outcomes, the purpose of this quality improvement (QI) project was to increase utilization of the PB by NTSV laboring patients and to reduce labor hours by implementing an instructional video course and poster display on the intrapartum unit.

Supporting Framework

Recommendations by the Committee on Quality of Health Care in America and the Institute of Medicine (2001) included an emphasis on solving the quality and safety issues of health care through improvement science. Hospital systems and health policy have since adopted quality improvement strategies and incorporated them into practice in order to provide high standards and high value of care. One model for improvement used by quality professionals is the Institute for Healthcare Improvement's (IHI) Model for Improvement (MFI) (Langley et al., 2009). This model served as the methodological framework for this project.

The MFI, based on scientific principles, is data driven and has been successfully applied to various settings without necessitating significant training or use of complicated tools (Langley et al., 2009; Prybutok, 2018). Advancements in nursing care are essential to improve patient outcomes and that bedside nurses are ideally positioned to lead and manage quality projects (Flynn et al., 2017). The MFI provides a framework for this project by applying scientific principles of quality improvement and using MFI tools to survey existing processes and to determine if changes result in an improvement (Langley et al., 2009).

Rapid, small scale testing and evaluation of change are the foundation of this model through a Plan, Do, Study, Act (PDSA) cycle (see Figure 1) of improvement. This model emphasizes a continuous cycle of "trial-and-learning methodology" (Langley et al., pp. 24-25). The PDSA model was created by the statistician Dr. Walter Shewhart in 1939 and further

developed by the physicist William Deming in 1982 (Moen, 2009; Provost & Murray, 2011). Deming's early work with leading Japanese industrialists resulted in profound organizational successes and was modeled with a priority of including managers and workers in the process (Pryor, 2006). Deming's use of the PDSA cycle resulted in efficient and low-cost production of quality goods (Moen, 2009).

The PDSA cycle was expanded by Moen, Nolan, and Provost (1991) by integrating the MFI theory and scientific principles of hypothesis testing into the planning step. The current MFI PDSA model includes three questions that guide project goals during the improvement process: (a) What are we trying to accomplish? (b) How will we know that a change is an improvement? and (c) What changes can we make that will result in an improvement? (Langley et al., 1994). Before beginning a PDSA cycle, the MFI emphasizes that in the process of identifying a change concept, existing knowledge and expertise on the subject are essential to develop and select the change idea (IHI, n.d.b). This principle of the MFI harkens back to Deming's emphasis on engaging the frontline staff into the improvement process. In this project, labor and delivery nursing input and feedback were identified as intrinsic aspects of refining the use of the PB and expected patient outcomes. This next section illustrates how the PDSA cycle applies to this project.

Goals of this project following the MFI (Langley et al., 2009) are as follows:

1. What are we trying to accomplish? Improved utilization of PB and decrease in NTSV labor hours.
2. How will we know that a change is an improvement? Increased documented PB use and decrease in labor hours when comparing average labor hours before and after instruction

and the poster display. The poster will depict photos of PB use with patients during labor and a project flow chart.

3. What changes can we make that will result in an improvement? Formal instruction during registered nurse (RN) staff meetings via an educational video with poster review. Begin PDSA cycles to improve PB utilization.

Figure 1

Plan, Do, Study Act, Cycle

Note. This figure displays the PDSA cycle and project steps. Adapted from Langley et al. (2009).

Plan

As part of planning, but also as a “living” tool that may be altered in all phases of the PDSA cycle, the MFI driver diagram (Figure 2) was completed to view the forces that influence the project’s goals. This depicts a visual display of the theory of improvement and contributes to decisions on project organization (Langley et al., 2009). This diagram considers the performance objectives that will be measured including the outcome, process, and balancing measure (IHI, n.d.a). The outcome measure is the patient centered goal. Because the leading indication for CS is associated with length of labor, measurement of number of labor hours was this project’s outcome measure. Given that the PB is one intervention employed in labor management, its utilization by nurses was identified as the process measurement. The second process measure was nursing knowledge pre- and post-education. A balancing measure captures the unintended consequences of a quality initiative. For this project, the balancing measure was the potential increased costs associated with stocking PBs.

Figure 2

Project Driver Diagram

Note. PB = peanut ball; Relationships among the outcomes, key drivers, and change ideas.

The planning phase of the PDSA outlines the project objectives, predictions of change, the details of who will be involved with the change, what the change will encompass, and where this change will occur (Langley et al., 1994; Moen et al., 1991). Achieving stakeholder support and institutional research approval were sought during this phase. Data measures were identified as outlined by the project goals and a data collection Excel file was created. A timeframe for baseline data collection of PB use and labor hours were identified. However, the COVID-19 pandemic resulted in suspension of all nonessential projects in the hospital setting and this phase of the project could not be completed. Instead, proxy measurements of chart documentation were employed and results were created.

Run charts were constructed to display the proxy historical data of PB use and NTSV labor hours on the unit. A run chart is a simple graph that visually outlines how data of interest has changed over time and allows for data analysis in preparation for the PDSA change (Langley et al., 2009). The run chart can identify if data are being influenced by random (predictable) or non-random (unexpected) events (Provost & Murray, 2011). For this project, the use of proxy PB and labor hours in NTSV patients were analyzed for variation between the 4-weeks before provision of education and 4-weeks after. The current cost of PBs was to be calculated for one month at baseline and after the project. However, due to the pandemic restrictions, this information was not attainable. The use of proxy data enabled the author to demonstrate the type of statistical testing and run chart documentation that would be needed when this project was resumed following COVID-19 pandemic restrictions.

The plan stage of the MFI model includes the generation of a hypothesis of the project outcomes (Langley et al., 2009). It was proposed that this PDSA cycle would result in increased knowledge regarding PB use in labor and higher use of the PB by the nursing staff as well as a

decrease in overall NTSV patient labor hours.

Do

Steps in this phase of PDSA include a performance of the change and recording of events as the change unfolds (Langley et al., 2009). A project poster and MFI flow diagram were completed. A flow diagram (see Figure 3) is a tool that portrays the project process and facilitates communication between the author and nursing staff during the project rollout (Provost & Murray, 2011). Two copies of the same poster were developed and contain pictures demonstrating the use of the PB in a patient bed in different laboring positions and the project flow diagram. When the project resumes, they will be displayed in the nursing break room and in the supply room where RNs retrieve the PB.

A knowledge survey tool was developed by the author to be given to nurses regarding PB usage in labor prior to staff education during regularly scheduled meetings. Copies of the education video were also sent to the obstetric nursing staff for their review. Upon implementation of the project, instruction via video on the appropriate use and positioning of the PB with laboring patients will be shown by the author during nursing staff meetings for both day and night shifts. Concomitantly, nurse champions will be solicited. These champions will reinforce project information with staff members throughout their shifts. The nurse champions will be emailed a copy of the poster and lesson outline by the author.

Figure 3*Peanut Ball Project Flow Chart*

Note. RN = Registered Nurse. Project Flow Chart of peanut ball project process. Adapted from Bassard & Ritter (2018).

Study

According to the MFI, the study step of the PDSA cycle calculates and interprets data pre- and post-change (Provost and Murray, 2011). After the project, data were obtained from the post-course knowledge survey. PB use and labor hours were compared pre- and post-intervention implementation. Run and Shewhart charts were utilized to interpret data over time and evaluated if the project had any impact on the outcome measure (labor hours) and process measure (PB use). The balancing measure (associated cost of PB) was also addressed (cost per PB X number

used pre- and post-project implementation). Named after the scientist, Dr. Walter Shewhart (Lloyd, n.d.a), these charts allow for determining the effect of change produced by a PDSA cycle through statistical measurements (Provost & Murray, 2011). This study phase revealed if the PB course and interventions led to increased PB use and less labor hours and if the study hypotheses should be rejected or accepted (Langley et al., 2009).

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic and associated stoppage of all non-essential work, data were analyzed using proxy data. The balancing measure (cost of PBs) was not able to be obtained, hence no control chart was able to be created to illustrate PB cost. The outcome measure of labor hours was constructed using proxy data. As illustrated, since more PBs were being placed post-education, the total number of labor hours was higher post-project. A run chart was created to better visualize the process of PB placement. A Shewhart control chart was not able to be generated as the average number of PBs placed per unit of measurement was less than four. Subsequently, a run chart was produced to examine if the changes resulted in an improvement. Other proxy data were recorded into an Excel spreadsheet and studied using the appropriate statistical analysis.

Act

In the act step of a PDSA cycle, the knowledge gained from the previous steps are considered and it is determined if a new PDSA cycle is necessary to achieve success (Langley et al., 2009). If no change in PB use and labor hours occurs, adapting previous methods for improvement and repeating PDSA cycles with different change ideas will take place. Conversely, if this project results in more PB use and fewer labor hours, the facilitation of project sustainability is part of the Act process. Improvement science espouses a philosophy that improvement should be both ongoing and sustainable (Langley et al., 2009). During this time,

efforts to support consistent nursing use of the PB and monitoring labor outcomes as part of the goal towards long-term change takes place. It was the author's objective that by involving the obstetric nurses in every step of this project, as observed in other settings by Shafer & Aziz (2013), nurses will lead future quality driven initiatives and transform obstetric care at this facility. Unfortunately, due to the current pandemic, this project was unable to reach this step of the IHI Model for Improvement.

Review of Literature

A review of the literature was conducted using the databases: PubMed, CINAHL/EBSCO, Cochrane Library, Google Scholar, and California State University, Fullerton Library OneSearch. Search terms for PB literature included: “peanut ball and pregnancy,” “peanut ball and labor length,” and “peanut ball,” and “cesarean section.” Research on continuous labor support (CLS) used the following search terms: “*continuous labor support*,” “*labor support*,” and “*labor outcomes*,” “*labor support and cesarean section*,” “*labor support and length of labor*.” Labor nursing skills and knowledge acquisition was investigated using the search terms “*nursing knowledge and labor*,” “*nursing skills and labor*,” and “*obstetric nursing education*.” Limits on the search included English language only with no limit on time frame.

Overview

The birth of a child can be a highly memorable event for the patient and family. In the US, most women will give birth in an inpatient hospital setting (MacDorman & Declercq, 2019) and will be cared for by a labor and delivery nurse. Labor nurses who work on these units initiate multiple forms of non-pharmacological interventions in the process of caring for a laboring patient. These interventions are a fundamental professional aspect of the labor nurse. Nurses assist the laboring patient with the inherent personal and emotional aspects of birth and associated pain experienced in the process. Some actions like application of heat or cold therapy and massage are initiated by the nurse to provide comfort and reduce labor pain (Simkin & Bolding, 2004). Additionally, nurses provide education to the patient and family throughout the laboring process. Obstetric nurses are solely responsible for assisting the patient towards a successful vaginal birth with position changes, physical support, coaching and encouragement. One type of non-pharmacological nursing intervention is the use of devices like the PB that is

placed between the laboring patient's thighs, usually after a patient receives epidural anesthesia. The use of the PB assists with keeping the pelvis open and is thought to help facilitate descent of the baby (Johnston, 1997; Zwelling, 2010).

During labor, the amount of time spent at the bedside and the types of nursing interventions that are initiated by the nurse are individualized and on a continuum. Some nurses practice at the bedside and chart in the room alongside the laboring patient while simultaneously giving care. Other nurses have a workflow of documenting outside the room or may have a workflow that does not allow for synchronized care. Some observational studies have estimated that labor nurses spend an average of 12.4% to 33% of their time providing supportive care like instructional, emotional, and physical support with the least amount of time in the physical supportive realm (Gale et al., 2001; Miltner, 2002). The concept of CLS includes definitions of nursing and non-nursing provision of physical, emotional, and social needs of a woman in labor (Bohren et al., 2017; Sauls, 2002). CLS is recommended by professional nursing and medical organizations (AWHONN, 2018; ACOG, SMFM & Caughey et al., 2014). However, due to staffing issues (Simpson et al., 2019) and technology responsibilities (Zwelling, 2008), CLS and interventions may not be accomplished. Nurses' location of work and unit culture also may impact how CLS is provided and which patients receive CLS (Payant et al., 2008). If the nurses are not willing or able to provide CLS, there is also less opportunity to initiate and manage supportive measures like the PB. As the following review of the literature illustrates, CLS is associated with improved outcomes. However, research gaps exist in analyzing the role of nurses as providers of CLS.

Peanut Ball Use and Labor Outcomes

A total of four randomized control trials (RCTs) wherein the PB was the intervention in the experimental group were identified (Evans & Cremering, 2016; Mercier & Kwan, 2018; Roth et al., 2016; Tussey et al., 2015). A quasi-experimental designed study that compared prospective PB users in labor to historical data without PBs was also ascertained (Hickey & Savage, 2019). Consistently, the placement of the PB during labor was the independent variable in all studies. With the exception of the Mercier and Kwan (2018) study that placed the PB when the patient was at least six centimeters dilated, all the other studies placed the PB at the time of epidural anesthesia. The mode of delivery (CS or vaginal) was evaluated in all but the Roth et al. (2016) research study. All studies evaluated the use of PBs and the impact on the length of labor except Mercier and Kwan (2018) who evaluated cervical dilation rate. All used convenient samples and participants were similar across four studies in that they were 18 years or older. Tussey et al. (2015) included women younger than 18 with consent. Two studies (Hickey and Savage, 2019; Tussey et al., 2015) excluded women who needed magnesium sulfate for hypertension in pregnancy, thus limiting the findings to lower risk patients not requiring this medication. Three studies (Evans & Cremering, 2016; Mercier & Kwan, 2018; Roth et al., 2016) had a small sample size that restricted the power and increased the risk of Type II errors, while Hickey and Savage (2019) and Tussey et al. (2015) had adequate participants. Settings varied geographically. Three studies took place in academic settings, and the other in a Magnet designated facility. Two studies limited the investigation to primigravidas only (Evans & Cremering, 2016; Mercier & Kwan, 2018). All data were collected via chart audits, except in two studies (Evans & Cremering, 2016; Hickey & Savage, 2019), where it was not clear how data were obtained. All studies had bias potential as the nurses, providers, and participants could

not be blinded to the PB intervention. Across studies, there was variance in how nurses were educated on using PB and in the details of PB placement.

There were conflicting findings on the rate of CS and PB use. CS was significantly lower in the PB group in two studies. In Hickey and Savage (2019), the odds ratio of having a CS was 50% less in the PB group versus the historical non-PB users (0.505, 95% CI [0.303, 0.843]). However, the internal validity of this study was weakened with the use of a historical group. Tussey et al. (2015) also found significant differences in CS rate ($p = 0.011$); although the PB group began the study with higher parity and more dilated than participants in the control group. Mercier and Kwan (2018) found no difference in the CS rate between the groups of nulliparous women. While not statistically significant, clinically, the primary CS rate for NTSV patients using the PB in Evans and Cremering (2016) was 23.1% compared to 31% in the usual care NTSV participants.

Discrepancies were also found when examining the length of labor. Tussey et al. (2015) found significantly shorter first ($p = .006$) and second ($p = <.001$) stages of labor regardless of parity in the PB group. The first stage of labor was shortened significantly for primigravidas using the PB (116.63 minutes shorter), but pushing time was longer for the same group in the Roth et al. (2016) study. Hickey and Savage (2019) saw no differences in the length of the first stage of labor between the PB users and the control group. Evans and Cremering (2016) did not see any difference in “length of labor” but it was unclear if that was the first or second stage of labor or a summation of the total length of labor. Mercier and Kwan (2018) did not demonstrate a difference between cervical dilatation rates between the PB group and the control group.

In addition, a recent meta-analysis (MA) completed by Grenvik et al. (2019), computed a subgroup analysis for nulliparous women who used a PB in labor for the above mentioned RCTs

(Evans & Cremering, 2016; Mercier & Kwan, 2018; Roth et al., 2016; Tussey et al., 2015). This MA revealed a decreased risk of CS, RR = 0.77, 95% CI [0.57, 1.03], and higher chance of vaginal delivery, RR = 1.14, 95% CI [1.00, 1.29]. Although not statistically significant, this MA found that the first stage of labor was shorter in patients who used the PB which is clinically important. These results reflect a high possibility that the PB is a useful tool to use with nulliparous patients.

A quality improvement project demonstrated a decreased primary CS rate in NTSV patients to be lower after five months of introducing a PB to patients with epidurals (Logan & Stettler, 2019). The NTSV CS rate decreased from 19.5% to 16.2 %. This project involved education of nursing staff on safe PB use and placement with periodic updates and heavy involvement of the nursing staff in the quality improvement process. Of note, the quality improvement project had a small sample size limiting the generalizability of these results.

Nursing Support and Labor Outcomes

When the labor nurses are present and providing CLS to the patient he/she can initiate therapies that support labor progress. Only two RCTs were carried out in which laboring patients received CLS by nurses (Gagnon et al., 1997; Hodnett et al., 2002). Results of CLS by RNs varied between the studies with both using convenience sampling. CS and length of labor were the dependent variables in both studies. NTSV patients were the participants in Gagnon et al. (1997). Hodnett et al. (2002) had a sample inclusion criterion of 34 or more weeks of gestation, previous CS, and twin pregnancy. All data were obtained via chart review. NTSV patients were slightly less likely to have a CS in the Gagnon et al. (1997) study when they received one-to-one nursing support during labor, RR = 0.86, 95% CI [0.54, 1.36]. However, this study had a very

low NTSV CS rate in both arms of the study (13.9% in the RN CLS group and 16.2% in the RN usual care group).

The Hodnett et al., study (2002) had a large sample size ($N = 6,915$) comparing laboring women who received CLS by RNs ($n = 3454$) and those who did not receive CLS and was conducted across Canada and the US. Nurses completed a two-day training on labor support taught by a labor nurse and doula. A doula is a non-medical person who provides emotional, physical, and knowledge support to women in labor (Doulas of North America, 2020). In this study, CLS was defined as the trained nurse being present with the laboring patient at least 80% of the time the nurse was assigned to that patient. No further details were given about the type of supportive measures provided. This study revealed no difference in CS rates or duration of labor between the two groups.

An RCT, as an experimental design, has high internal validity. However, the issue with Hodnett's findings is a lack of generalizability to the NTSV patient population. In this study, nurses cared for preterm patients, patients with a history of previous CS, and twin pregnancies. In fact, in the CLS arm of the study there were twice as many women with twin pregnancies (0.6%) vs the control group (0.3%) and a higher percentage of women with a previous CS. Although low, these conditions are known high-risk factors for CS and may have influenced the outcomes. Hodnett et al. (2002) also surveyed participants regarding 23 nursing interventions prior to discharge home (96% participation). Survey responses confirmed that the CLS patients noticed their nursing care and reported significantly more nursing support during their labor.

Other studies have examined midwives and not nurses as CLS providers. Kashanian (2010) demonstrated a statistically significant difference in the NTSV CS rate ($p = 0.003$) and shorter first ($p < 0.001$) and second ($p = 0.003$) stages of labor with continuous midwifery

support in Iran. However, the experimental group also received a private room, could eat and drink, and received education throughout their labor which was not given to the control group compromising the internal validity of this study. Another study from Australia randomized nulliparous laboring women to continuous midwifery support or epidural anesthesia that resulted in a faster labor but no difference in CS rate in the midwife group (Dickinson et al., 2002). As this study compared midwifery care to epidural anesthesia that is known to increase the length of all stages of labor (Anim-Somuah, et al., 2018), these conclusions are not compelling and considered weak evidence as the researchers compared two interventions in two unequal patient populations.

A Cochrane Library systematic review (Bohren et al., 2017) of CLS included the previous four studies in addition to older studies that utilized a midwife (Breart et al., 1992) or a midwife student (Hemminki et al., 1990). CLS was defined as, “some combination of comfort measures, emotional support, provision of information, and advocacy on behalf of the woman, provided from at least early labor (before 6 cm dilation) or within one hour of hospital admission (for admission with greater than or equal to 6 cm dilation), through at least the birth, and provided by a person whose sole responsibility is to provide support to the woman, as continuously as practical in a given context” (Bohren et al., 2017, p. 7). Overall, this systematic review demonstrated a decreased length of labor, RR = -0.69, 95% CI [-1.04, -0.34], and increased chance of vaginal birth in the CLS group versus usual care, RR = 1.05, 95% CI [1.01, 1.09].

According to the MA completed by Bohren et al. (2017), support of women in labor by doulas or other non-clinical individuals has been shown to decrease labor length and the CS rate. Nurses are qualified to initiate many of the same supportive measures as non-clinical individuals.

However, due to other nursing responsibilities, nursing care is often interrupted. To date, there are persistent research gaps in evaluating labor and delivery nursing practice and relationships to maternal outcomes.

Labor Nursing Acquired Knowledge and Skills

The Association of Women's Health, Obstetric and Neonatal Nurses (AWHONN) advocates for labor nurses to advance their education about nursing interventions and labor support tools (AWHONN, 2018). Nurses have voiced opinions that educational endeavors such as workshops and in-service opportunities would increase job confidence and capability to provide CLS and initiate non-pharmacological interventions in labor (Davies & Hodnett, 2001). An educational program that focused on improving CLS nursing skills with use of a professional poster exhibiting nonpharmacologic labor interventions demonstrated increased understanding after attending the class (Murn, 2018). In Alton et al. (2012) labor nurses from novice to expert working in an inner-city academic setting participated in an educational program focused on bringing benefits shown in the literature of non-pharmacologic CLS interventions into their work setting. Overall, nurses involved in this project found the CLS knowledge useful and impactful in the direct care given to patients in labor. It remains unknown if these educational programs had a lasting impact on these units and if the labor nurses were able to continue these practice changes.

Conclusion

A PB is likely a feasible, appropriate, and useful tool to support local and national efforts to decrease the CS rate in the US. Investigations of PB use with larger samples, standardization of PB usage, and consistent training on PB implementation in various obstetric settings will produce more reliable results and trustworthy conclusions. Prolonged labor is the leading indication for CS. Hence, a continued focus of research should strive to evaluate the potentially

valuable intervention of the PB in NTSV patients to reduce laboring hours, thus preventing primary CS and subsequent sequelae.

Nurses play a vital role in assisting women to give birth. Research gaps exist on nursing care as an independent influencer on labor outcomes. Qualitative research has examined the phenomena of nurse level of expertise, communication tactics with providers, and impact on delivery finding themes of negotiation for more time to initiate nursing therapies that assist with vaginal delivery (Edmonds & Jones, 2012). Each labor nurse has a unique style of management and various ways of supervising a laboring patient. Although research is still emerging, current studies suggest contrasting CS rates between nurses. In a retrospective study of 72 nurses and 3,031 NTSV patients, a woman's risk of CS was nearly three times higher when assigned to certain nurses in the same setting (Edmonds, et al., 2017). Regardless of the work environment, as part AWHONN's clinical competency, every professional labor nurse must engage with various learning modalities to be successful at employing CLS and using nursing interventions like the PB appropriately and correctly (AWHONN, 2019).

Methods

Project Purpose

The purpose of this QI project was to increase nursing placement of the PB as part of nursing care and support of patients in labor. PB use in labor has been demonstrated to decrease labor time and reduce the risk of primary CS (Grenvik et al., 2019). According to the perinatal core measures at the hospital where the initial planning of this QI project took place, the NTSV CS rate was 25.1% which is above the recommended benchmarks set by national, state, and professional organizations (ACOG, SMFM, & Caughey et al., 2014; Lagrew et al., 2018; Smith et al., 2016). PBs were accessible to the nurses directly on the unit or ordered by hospital supplies and were available to every laboring patient. Prior to this project, the labor and delivery nurses had not received any formal instruction on PB use. As witnessed by the author and substantiated by administration, there was inconsistent use of this device by nurses. Hence, the author determined an area of need for improved use of this device.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, academic projects were cancelled at the planned institution. Therefore, this project could not be implemented during the required academic deadline for the DNP project. In order to demonstrate the evaluation component (study) planned for this project, proxy numbers were used to illustrate how best to analyze the type of data and information that should be collected.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical components that were considered included seeking Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval from the project facility site and from the California State University, Long Beach. This would have occurred prior to project commencement. Additionally, the author would have sought formal approval for the project from the department of obstetrics' nursing

administration and nursing education with participation from the labor and delivery nursing staff voluntary. In order to collect pre-and post-survey information, obtaining the participant email addresses would be necessary. This information would be held securely and not shared per the SurveyMonkey™ rules and regulations (Gitlan, n.d.). The author planned to keep login information from the online survey tool confidential. In the analysis of the responses, all email addresses were to be kept private. If a need for printing emails was required, all hardcopies were to be locked up with author only access. After collection of the post-survey data, all email information was to be destroyed. Nurses would be asked to self-volunteer as designated PB project champions. The educational video (Torrance, 2020) would be sent to the nursing staff using their work emails.

NTSV patients would be identified from the photocopies of the handwritten birth log maintained by the labor and delivery staff. The medical record number (MRN) of the NTSV patients would be recorded and de-identified, and data extracted through the electronic medical record (EMR) on an institutional computer. Via this chart review, the NTSV patients who had PBs placed would be identified and examined for the number of PBs placed, the total number of labor hours, labor outcomes, Certified Nurse Midwife (CNM) or Medical Doctor (MD) provider, and Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) admission. The name of the RNs caring for the NTSV patients who placed the PB would be required to evaluate change of practice, but no other personal information on the RNs would be collected. Each RN name would be de-identified by replacement of a name with a number.

Setting

This project was to be implemented in a hospital facility in southern California in a city with a population of 282,572 residents (US Census Bureau, n.d.). The inpatient labor and

delivery unit has a birth rate of approximately 250 births/month, and the hospital achieved Magnet status, a designation by the American Nursing Credentialing Center (ANCC) recognizing hospitals that support excellence in nursing care, nursing leadership, education, and patient quality of care (ANCC, n.d.). There are 70 labor and delivery RNs who staff the unit. The labor and delivery nurses follow AWHONN staffing guidelines that include one-to-one nursing care for patients in active labor (AWHONN, 2011).

Approximately 70% of laboring patients receive epidural anesthesia. The NICU is a level two nursery equipped to care for infants aged 32 weeks of gestation and higher (American Academy of Pediatrics Committee on Fetus and Newborn, 2012). Healthcare providers are staffed in-house and include CNMs and obstetrician/gynecologists (OB/GYNs) MDs, anesthesiologists, and neonatologists. The CNMs work Monday through Friday from 0800 until midnight. During the weekends, CNMs maintain 24-hour coverage at this facility. The OB/GYN MDs staff the unit on a continual basis. CNMs and OB/GYN MDs work collaboratively on the unit with one OB/GYN MD and one CNM designated as principal providers on the birthing unit. However, CNMs perform the majority of the vaginal births and independently manage and attend most of the deliveries of low-risk, NTSV laboring patients.

Resources Needed

To successfully implement a project as the one described, the following resources must be provided. Personnel necessary include labor and delivery nursing staff and volunteer nurse champions. Nursing staff time during times of instruction and when the nurse champions assist staff nurses with PB use with patients must be taken into consideration. Technological resources include access to the EPIC/Health Connect EMR for data recording of labor hours and PB placement for documentation by the nurse in the patient labor chart. Information technology (IT)

staff support is critical with capturing data. The author suggests the use of the software Microsoft Office Excel, QI Macros, and Intellectus Statistics to analyze data.

Although not formally studied, PB size choice varies on patient height and comfort of patient (Lythgoe, 2014). Current standard of care requires the labor nurse to choose the correct PB(s) for their patient(s). There must be stock of PBs of various sizes on the birthing unit and access to electricity for inflation of the PB. Nursing time to complete this task is considered essential to a successful project of this nature. Wall space to display posters should be used to display the project poster and flow chart in the nursing break room and in the area where PBs are stocked.

Participants

This project focused on educating the obstetric nursing staff on the use of the PB for the NTSV laboring patient population. Therefore, the author identified what was to be the participation inclusion and exclusion criteria. All labor and delivery RNs employed at this facility who provide direct patient care for laboring women were eligible to participate in this project. Multiparous, preterm, multiple gestation, high-risk, and/or non-vertex patients and those under 18 were excluded as project participants. Data from NTSV patients who did not receive PB and NTSV patients not in labor were also excluded.

Data Collection Methods

As part of the required nursing documentation of patient progress in labor during the implementation of a similar project, the time labor commences and ends are recorded by the nurse. The time labor begins is generally defined as regular uterine contractions that are associated with progressive and objective cervical dilation (Liao et al., 2005). Labor ends with the birth of the infant. Nurses also record in the EMR the time PBs were placed. Prior to project

initiation baseline data for NTSV patients, including labor hours, PB use, RN name, NICU admission, and MD or CNM provider, would be obtained through the EMR by a QI investigator at least two times a week. Any personal information must be de-identified through number assignments and recorded onto a spreadsheet. In QI projects, data collection and display should be completed frequently in order to identify if data truly fluctuate and when/if changes occur in a process (Lloyd, n.d.). The same data would then be collected for 4-weeks after project implementation.

For the purposes of this project, an online tool SurveyMonkey™ would be used to collect baseline knowledge of PB use prior to instruction on the PB use and poster display. The author drafted an email to be sent out to all eligible nurses by their managers before the course began. The email had a hospital issued address with the informational sheet (see Appendix A) and survey attached (see Appendix B). This survey was projected to take approximately one to five minutes to complete and was written at college graduate level according to the Flesch Kincaid readability index (Online - Utility.org, n.d.).

Project Implementation

Due to the restrictions with Covid-19, an educational video was completed with class content outlines (Torrance, 2020). This video was reviewed by five labor and delivery nurses for content, clarity, and congruence with knowledge survey. There was 100% agreement achieved among all domains.

The video course by Torrance (2020) began with a brief overview of research findings on PB usage. Next, proper placement of the PB with another person acting as a patient was demonstrated. A side lying position and a side lying in a semi-prone position that may facilitate rotation of a baby who is in the occiput posterior position (CMQCC, 2018; Lythgoe, 2014) was

reviewed. The course includes a reminder to the nursing staff to avoid PBs in those with hip injuries, adhere to movement per hospital protocol, and to chart when the PB is placed. Consideration of obtaining a PB for every NTSV laboring patient upon admission was suggested in the video. Lastly, a demonstration on how to inflate or deflate the PB was provided.

The video would be emailed to nursing staff and could be watched and reviewed as desired. Additionally, the author would attend virtual obstetrical nursing staff meetings whereby the video would have been shown and contents reviewed by the author.

Part of the project implementation included display of a poster depicting the PB positions reviewed in the course along with a flow chart outline of the project. This would be displayed in the nurses' break room and where he/she retrieves the PB device prior to placement. A copy of the class outline, poster, flow chart would be emailed to the PB nurse champions. The PB poster used as a reference in the course (Appendix D) and project flow chart (Appendix E) were to be placed on the unit where nurses obtain PBs and in the nursing break area accessible throughout the month of data collection.

After project completion, the survey should be emailed once more to the nurses who completed the pre-survey with identical questions in a different order. The process of scoring the survey must be congruent both pre- and post-project.

Initially, as a balance measure, the author desired to understand the financial costs associated with PB stocking and purchasing for the intrapartum unit. Due to the project being halted secondary to the COVID-19 pandemic, this information was not obtainable.

Measures/Tools

In implementing a project such as this, data from the staff knowledge survey and informational sheet would be recorded onto a MS Excel spreadsheet. EMR chart audit can be

used to extract data on the number of PBs used, labor hours, birth outcome, NICU admission and CNM or MD delivery for NTSV patients using PBs. Labor hours calculated from the EMR from the onset of labor to the birth of the baby in hours and would be recorded onto a data collection spreadsheet.

An educational video using the platform Vimeo (Torrance, 2020) was completed in lieu of the intended in-person course due to the COVID-19 pandemic and is available by contacting the author and via the Vimeo website. The video covers key concepts regarding PB efficacy, placement, documentation, and safe use for the RN. This video followed the class outline (Appendix C) and was reviewed by five labor and delivery nurses for clarity, consistency, and relevancy of information. The result provided to the author was 100% agreement for these qualities. While the number of views of the video is available, to protect privacy of the viewers, identification of the viewers is not possible on this platform.

Evaluation

Survey results are then studied by comparing the pre- and post-project survey results. Only those nurses who completed the pre-survey, watched the educational video, and completed the post-survey should be included in the statistical analysis. Correct answers can be analyzed with SurveyMonkey™ scoring a gross number of correct answers. Scores of individual nurses' correct answers can be recorded and stored. Post-project implementation, aggregate data on percentages of correct answers pre- and post-project would then be calculated. Descriptive statistics, Spearman correlations, ANOVAs, *t*-testing, and McNemar's Chi-Square analysis can then be calculated on data obtained from the survey. The results from the use of proxy data are found in the subsequent section of this paper and demonstrate the type of analytical testing and the calculations necessary to evaluate the effectiveness of the PB as a nursing intervention.

As a visual illustration of findings, proxy data for PBs used were plotted on run (control) charts with time variable (daily) on the x-axis and specified measures (NTSV PB use) on the y-axis. After at least 10 data points, the median of the PBs used was calculated and visible as a horizontal line through the data points. Proxy data were analyzed by the MFI run chart rules and random (predictable) or nonrandom (unexpected) events (Provost & Murray, 2011) were identified. Non-random patterns were indicated by evidence of certain patterns of data points and rules called shifts, trends, too many/too few runs or astronomical data points. If non-random events like shifts or trends were indicated by the data in the control charts, this signaled evidence of a process improvement (Provost & Murray, 2011). For this project, all PDSA cycles and events were noted on the charts.

The average total labor hours of NTSV PB users, presented as proxy data, were analyzed pre- and post-project through descriptive and inferential statistical tests including *t*-tests. Labor outcomes, CNM or MD provider, NICU admission, nurse identification, week of the study, and days of the week were evaluated with Chi-square testing and *t*-tests.

Results

All data and results presented are proxy data due to all DNP projects being suspended during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Pre-Implementation Data and Activities

Knowledge Survey

Characteristics of Nurses Completing Pre- and Post-Project Survey

The PB knowledge survey was distributed to labor and delivery nurses via email from their manager. A total of 40 labor and delivery staff nurses (57%) completed both the pre- and post-project survey and were included in this project. Most nurses (45%) completing the survey had an associate degree in nursing (ADN), 18 (35%) had a bachelor's degree in nursing (BSN) and 8 held a master's degree in nursing (MSN). None of the participating RNs held a doctorate degree. Most participants completing the survey had been practicing nursing for 4-8 years, $n = 19$, (48%) and the most prevalent age was 36 years and older ($n = 12$, 30%). See Table 1.

Table 1

Characteristics of Nurses Completing Survey

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
Highest Degree Achieved		
ADN	18	45.00
BSN	14	35.00
MSN	8	20.00
Years of Nursing		
1-3 years	12	30.00
4-8 years	19	47.50
9 years or more	9	22.50
Age		
20-25	10	25.00

26-30	7	17.50
31-35	11	27.50
36 and older	12	30.00

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%. ADN = Associate degree in nursing; BSN = bachelor's degree in nursing; MSN = Master's degree in nursing.

Baseline Nursing Knowledge Survey Statistics

Of the four questions included on the survey, the participants answered an average of 1.70 questions correctly. The summary statistics can be found in Table 2. This indicated areas of PB informational deficit and signaled an opportunity for knowledge improvement. The SD was 1.09, indicating variability of baseline PB knowledge among the staff.

Table 2

Total Pre-Project Correct Survey Answers

Variable	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>n</i>
Correct Pre-Project Answers	1.70	1.09	40

Note: *M* = Mean; *SD* = standard deviation; *n* = partial sample size.

Analysis of Pre-Project Survey Scores, Years of Nursing, and Age

A Spearman correlation analysis was conducted between correct answers pre-project and years of nursing experience and age. Years of nursing was aggregated to a range of 1-3, 5-8, or 9 or more years of nursing and ranges of age were 20-25, 26-30, 31-35, and 36 years and older. The result of the correlation was examined based on an alpha value of 0.05. There were no significant correlations between any pairs of these variables. Table 3 presents the results of the correlation.

Table 3*Pre-Project Correct Survey Answers Correlated with Years of Nursing and Age*

Correlative Testing	r_s	95% CI	P
Years of Nursing (1-3, 5-8, 9 or more years)	-0.09	[-0.39, 0.23]	.596
Age (20-25, 26-30, 31-35, 36 and older)	-0.07	[-0.38, 0.24]	.650

Note. $n = 40$; CI = Confidence Interval; p = probability statistic; r_s = Spearman's rank order correlation coefficient

Nursing Degree and Pre-Test Survey Scores

An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to determine whether there were significant differences in correct pre-test scores and highest nursing degree achieved, age and years of nursing. As stated, most participants held an ADN. The results of this analysis were significant ($p = .038$) indicating differences among the survey scores and levels of education. Higher numbers of pre-project survey questions answered correctly correlated with the degree advancement. The means and standard deviations from these calculations are presented in Table 4.

Table 4*Pre-Project Correct Survey Answers and Nursing Degree*

Degree	M	SD	N
AND	1.33	1.03	18
BSN	1.71	0.73	14
MSN	2.50	1.41	8

Note. ADN = Associate Nursing Degree; BSN = Bachelor of Science in Nursing; MSN = Master of Science Degree in Nursing.

Additionally, paired t -tests were calculated between each pair of measurements to further examine the differences among the variables of nursing degree, age, and years of nursing. The mean number of correct answers pre-project was significantly smaller for nurses with ADNs (M

= 1.33, $SD = 1.03$) versus nurses with MSNs ($M = 2.50$, $SD = 1.41$), $p = .029$). No other significant effects were found.

Baseline/Pre-project Peanut Ball Use, Labor Hours, and Birth Outcomes

There were 64 NTSV PB users whose data were analyzed pre-project. At baseline, the median number of PBs placed by RNs in NTSV patients was 1.6/day (Figure 4). Of the 70 staff nurses, 21 RNs placed PBs pre-project. The highest number of PBs placed by an individual RN pre-project was 7.

At baseline, the average NTSV total labor hours were 12.13 ($SD = 5.51$). The primary NTSV CS rate in PB users was 22% with most of these patients delivering vaginally (75%). In this group, five babies (7.81%) were admitted to the NICU. CNMs attended 75% of the births, while MDs attended 25% of the pre-project births.

Post-Implementation Data and Activities

Knowledge Survey

Summary statistics were calculated for total correct answers post-education. The observations for total post-project correct answers had a mean of three out of a total four of questions. This was a significant improvement from the pre-project scores.

A two-tailed paired samples t -test was conducted to examine whether the mean difference was significantly different from zero pre- and post-education. The result of the two-tailed paired samples t -test was significant ($p < .001$), indicating the null hypothesis (PB knowledge will not be improved by educational project) can be rejected. The results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5

Two-Tailed Paired Samples t-test for the Difference Between Correct Survey Answers Pre- and Post-Project

Total Correct Pre-Project		Total Correct Post-Project		<i>T</i>	<i>P</i>
<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>		
1.70	1.09	3.00	0.64	-8.08	< .001

Note. $N = 40$. Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistic = 39. *d* represents Cohen's *d*; *M* = Mean; *p* = probability statistic; *SD* = standard deviation.

Post-Project Correct Survey Scores, Years of Nursing and Age

Spearman correlations analysis was conducted to examine differences between total correct post-project survey and years of nursing or age of the participant. The result of this analysis detected no significant differences among years of nursing (95% CI -0.31, 0.31), $p = 1.00$, or age (95% CI -0.35, 0.27, $p = .794$).

Furthermore, ANOVAs were conducted to determine whether there were significant differences in correct post-project survey answers and age or years of nursing. The results of these calculations demonstrated that post-project scores were similar between the nurses with different years of nursing experience ($p = 1.00$) and age ($p = .623$).

Nursing Degree and Post-Project Scores

An ANOVA was conducted to determine whether there were significant differences in post-project correct answers and nursing degree. The results indicated there were significant differences among nurses with different degrees ($p = .029$). The means and standard deviations from this analysis are presented in Table 6.

Paired *t*-tests were calculated between each pair of measurements to further examine the differences among the variables. Participants with ADN degrees were found to have a significantly lower number of correct answers ($M = 2.83$, $SD = 0.71$) post-project than nurses with a BSN ($M = 3.36$, $SD = 0.50$), $p = .048$. No other significant effects were found.

Table 6*Post-Project Correct Survey Answers and Nursing Degree*

Nursing Degree	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>N</i>
ADN	2.83	0.71	18
BSN	3.36	0.50	14
MSN	2.75	0.46	8

Note. ADN = Associate Nursing Degree; BSN = Bachelor of Science in Nursing; MSN = Master of Science Degree in Nursing.

Individual Test Question Analysis Pre- and Post-Project

In order to analyze differences in individual nursing survey performances pre-and post-project on the separate questions, McNemar's chi-Square test was conducted on each question. This analyzed proportions of incorrect and correct answers for pre- and post-questions. All knowledge survey questions demonstrated a significantly higher proportion of correct answers post-project than pre-project for each nurse (see Table 7).

Table 7*Frequencies of Incorrect and Correct Survey Answers Pre- and Post-Project*

Survey Question	PB decrease length of labor	PBs impact risk of CS	PBs are well studied	If baby is ROP what side do you turn the patient
<i>P</i>	.020	<.001	<.001	<.001

Note: *p* = probability statistic

Post-Project Peanut Ball Use, Labor Hours, and Birth Outcomes***Peanut Balls***

The median number of PBs placed in NTSV patients post-project was 2.4 PBs/day. There were five additional RNs placing PBs post-education than pre-education for a total of 25 RNs placing PBs. The highest number placed by an individual was 15.

A run chart (Figure 4) was created to further analyze the trend of PBs placed over time pre- and post-education. A C-Chart was not able to be constructed as there was an average of less

than 4 PBs used per measurement cycle which may increase the chance of a type II error, or a falsely negative conclusion (Polit, 2010). The run chart is a visual representation of a process. In order to analyze the run chart, application of the four rules for interpreting run chart data were employed. If one or more of these rules are depicted on the chart this suggests non-random variation or a change in the current process that is not attributable to usual variation of performance (Provost & Murray, 2011). Post-project, at day 51 there was a shift that occurred per run chart rules whereby six or more data points moved above the pre-project median value. This indicates that the elements as part of the project implementation resulted in an improvement of PB use (Langley et al., 2009). Additionally, PB use remained consistently above pre-project levels until day 67 then began to rise again. This may be a sign of sustained higher usage of the PB for the future.

Figure 4

Run Chart of Project Peanut Balls Placed Pre- and Post-Project

Labor Hours

There were 70 NTSV PB user data analyzed post-project. The average total labor hours in NTSV PB users decreased from 12.13 ($SD = 5.51$) to 10.21 ($SD = 4.91$) post-project. A two-tailed independent samples t -test was conducted to examine whether the mean of labor hours was

significantly different between pre- and post-project. The result was significant ($p = .035$), indicating the null hypothesis (nursing education and increased use of the PB to support labor has no effect on labor hours) can likely be rejected.

Table 8

Two-Tailed Independent Samples t-test for Labor Hours Pre- Vs. Post-Project

Variable	Pre-Project		Post-Project		<i>P</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	
Average Labor Hours	12.13	5.51	10.21	4.91	.035

N = 134.

Note. *M* = Mean; *SD* = standard deviation; *p* = probability statistic

Birth Outcomes

Similar to baseline data, the NTSV patients using the PB post-project had a high spontaneous vaginal delivery (SVD) rate ($n = 54, 77\%$). The NTSV PB users had a 21.4% CS rate which was slightly lower than the pre-project rate of 21.9%. A Chi-square Test of Independence did not demonstrate a significant difference ($p = .797$) in birth outcomes (SVD, CS, operative vaginal delivery [OVD]) between the pre- and post-project.

Of note, there was only one baby admitted to the NICU during this time. This was a reduction of NICU admissions by 6.44%. A Chi-square Test of Independence between NICU admissions pre- and post-project approached a significant relationship ($p = .074$) with a lower NICU admission rate in the post-project group.

Other findings

CNMs delivered slightly more babies post-project than pre-project (77.14% vs 75%). MDs delivered 22.86% of the post-project patient group which was 2% less than at baseline.

A two-tailed independent samples *t*-test was conducted to examine whether the mean of labor hours was significantly different between the CNM and MD (see Table 9). MDs had

significantly longer labors than CNMs (9.95 hours vs. 14.90 hours, $p = <.001$). However, in this practice setting it is customary for CNMs to primarily manage the low risk NTSV laboring population. This finding needs to be tempered with the knowledge that it was likely the CNM transferred care to the MD for dysfunctional labor.

Table 9

Two-Tailed Independent Samples t-test for Labor Hours by Provider

Variable	CNM		MD		P
	M	SD	M	SD	
Average Labor Hours	9.95	4.71	14.90	5.29	< .001
N = 134.					

Note. M = Mean; SD = standard deviation; p = probability statistic

Chi-square test of independence demonstrated no significant relationships associated with certain days of the week ($p = .157$) or weeks of the study ($p = .780$) and birth outcomes. This analysis also demonstrated a significant association with MD providers and CS or OVD while CNMs were more likely to have SVDs ($p < 0.001$).

Discussion

Due to COVID-19 restrictions, the study could not be conducted as planned. Proxy data was used to show expected/potential outcomes if this study had been conducted as expected as well as to guide future implementation plans.

Key Findings

The analysis of the proxy data revealed several key findings and, if they were not fictitious data, the results would be discussed in the following manner.

PB Knowledge Survey

To begin, across different ages and years of experience, RNs who participated in completing the survey scored significantly higher on the post-project survey than the pre-project survey. These scores suggest that the educational video course, poster, and reinforcement from nurse-champions increased nursing knowledge on the use of the PB during labor. Additionally, the proxy data provided evidence that individual nurses knew more correct answers on the post-project survey than the pre-project survey.

Over half of the RN staff completed both the pre- and post-project survey. This participation level reflects an interest in the staff to engage in activities that improve their abilities to provide labor support with nursing interventions. RNs are motivated to improve their labor support skills (Davis & Hodnett, 2001) and, to maintain competency, should stay up to date on the application of devices used in labor like the PB (AWHONN, 2019). Additionally, the RNs involved in this project illustrated their capacity to improve the level of PB understanding as evidenced by the higher correct scores post-project. As cited by Alton et al. (2012) and Murn (2018) this type of educational in-service and use of a visual aide like a poster can improve the nurse's skill and understanding of labor assistance and improve the care given at the bedside.

PB use

One goal of this QI project was to improve the consistency of PB use by the obstetric nursing staff through advancement of knowledge. Impressively, this educational intervention resulted in a 50% increase in the numbers of PBs placed by the RNs post-project than pre-project. This reinforces previous findings that indicate RNs will initiate new therapies like the PB to facilitate labor progress for their patients (Bell et al., 2017; Logan & Stettler, 2019). The highest number of PBs placed by any one nurse post-education increased from 7 to 15. These results imply that the education and support (video, poster, RN champion) available to the staff resulted in nurses becoming more apt to use the PB regularly.

Labor Hours in NSTV PB Users

Additionally, the fictitious data demonstrated that labors were shorter in the post-project group than the pre-project group. Labor length is an important variable to consider as it is the leading indication for primary CS (ACOG, SMFM, & Caughey et al., 2014). These findings were encouraging and confirmed previous study findings that demonstrated shorter labors when the PB is used in labor (Grenvik et al., 2019; Roth et al., 2016; Tussey et al., 2015). When the RN is placing a PB, the RN is taking time to care for the laboring patient. When laboring patients receive sustained help by a caregiver like a nurse, this results in shorter labors (Dickinson, 2002). Taken together, the combination of nursing support and regular use of the PB tool in labor can positively influence patient outcomes by shortening labor length and optimizing the chance of a vaginal delivery.

Birth Outcomes

Based on the fictitious data analysis, the CS rate was not significantly changed, going from 21.9% to 21.4%. From the start, the baseline NSTV CS rate in the PB users was already

below the national average of 25.9% (Martin et al., 2019) and below the NTSV CS quality benchmark rate of 23.9% (Smith et al., 2016). These lower rates were likely due to the exclusion of high-risk NTSV PB users. Given this project's short time frame, it is understandable that the CS rate would not be significantly altered. However, nurses who initiate therapies like the PB are engaging in elements of CLS and thus have the potential to influence labor outcomes with their supportive measures, which have been shown to impact CS risk (Bohren et al., 2017; Gagnon et al., 1997). Providing education to staff on the use of assistive techniques during labor, like using a PB, should be a high priority for nursing leadership. Long term, these nursing interventions serve to incrementally improve nursing care and patient satisfaction with care as well as increase the probability of fewer CS births, thus improving patient outcomes.

Other Findings

The proxy results demonstrated one surprising result, the association between nursing educational degrees and correct answers on survey questions. Pre-project, MSN-prepared nurses scored the highest, while post-project nurses holding BSNs had the most correct answers. Despite ADN staff being the most prevalent in staff numbers, this group had the least number of correct answers both pre- and post-survey.

Increasing the number of BSN-prepared nurses is a goal of the nursing profession (Altman et al., 2016; American Nurses Association, 2015). Evidence suggests that BSN-prepared nurses report feeling more prepared to meet the modern complex healthcare system's expectations of patient quality and safety (Djukic et al., 2019). Additionally, there are documented improved patient outcomes with nurses who attain a BSN degree (Altman et al., 2016). In this case, the differences in scores with a higher nursing education level may impact direct patient care during labor. The BSN and MSN-prepared RNs demonstrated an

understanding of the PB evidence in the literature and the correct usage of the device with patients. This level of PB understanding may translate into exceptional nursing attention and care of the laboring patient.

Limitations

There were several limitations to this study as it was originally designed and the ability to launch the project. First, project implementation was not actualized due to the COVID-19 pandemic, so data may not apply to settings without corroboration with future studies with authentic data. Hence, due to this project's nature by proxy, there is concern over the inherent statistical conclusion validity.

The sample size of both the RNs completing the surveys and the PB users was small, which increases the chance of a type II error or falsely concluding no significant relationships exist when in reality with larger sample sizes, one may find significant relationships existing between variables (Grove & Gray, 2019). Additionally, this project only included RNs at one facility and NTSV PB users. Thus, the project conclusions are not generalizable to different settings and are only applicable to similar RNs who work with low-risk NTSV patients.

Furthermore, information on RN race, ethnicity, prior experience using the PB, shift worked, video viewing, and communication with the PB RN champion while working was not collected as part of this project. Without this information, interpreting this project's success based upon RN PB knowledge improvement via the survey scores is limited to the factors that were analyzed (age, years of nursing, highest degree achieved).

CNMs attended most of the deliveries during the project. In this setting, CNMs care for lower risk laboring patients. MDs manage the term NTSV patients who are deemed high risk or those that have hypertensive disease of pregnancy, diabetes in pregnancy requiring medication,

or are morbidly obese. These high-risk patients were excluded from this project. Hence the generalizability and external validity of the conclusions are isolated to low-risk patients managed by CNMs.

While this project relied on the IHI MFI for the supporting framework, some aspects of this model were not feasible to be carried out due to the project by proxy. As such, PDSA cycles were not completed during the project implementation phase.

Biases

Biases inherently exist in any study or QI project. Bias influences project development and interpretation of the findings. Compared with the other 30 staff nurses who did not complete the surveys, there may have been unique characteristics and a tendency to answer questions a certain way, contributing to a response bias. Consequently, there was likely non-respondent bias for similar reasons.

Since the author wrote the survey, questionnaire bias is possible. This bias would influence how the nurses answered the questions. The nurses at the facility work alongside the author. This proximity could have contributed to inadvertent communication regarding the project before the respondents completed the survey. Lastly, there was a sample imbalance since this project only examined NTSV PB users and did not consider NTSV laboring patients who did not use the PB.

Recommendations

The COVID-19 pandemic mandated that contact between staff remain as virtual as possible. This requirement was an interesting aspect of this project to contemplate. Although the project data are not real, it is noteworthy that being required to facilitate nursing education virtually may be a feasible option for the future. The video-based format for an educational course, especially when the main topic is the use of a device, may provide learners certain advantages over the traditional classroom setting. The video course offered the nursing staff opportunity for repeated views, unlimited access, and flexibility in course scheduling.

Although total labor hours were measured, scrutinizing latent (prior to 6 cm dilation), active (from 6 cm -10 cm), and second stage (10 cm - delivery) labor may have resulted in clinically useful information on how the PB may or may not influence the length of different labor stages. Although the proxy data demonstrated that this project's main goal was successful in improving RN knowledge of the PB device and more frequent PB use, there were no controls on how and when the RN placed the PB with their laboring patients built into this project. If these facts were known, this project's results could bolster existing guidelines for PB use or result in more uniform use of the PBs by the RN staff.

To further examine PB impact on labor outcomes, reliance upon an experimental nursing study rather than QI methodology could render a more rigorous approach and improve the findings' reliability and validity. With an experimental project design, larger sample sizes and randomizing the participants provides better control of the individual characteristics that influence the outcomes (Polit & Beck, 2017). Randomization of PB users and non-PB users could yield useful information about the impact of the PB use on labor when the PB is the intervention, while the other variables that influence labor remain constant between the groups.

Additionally, if a researcher could be highly involved using the PB as an intervention, ensuring consistency in the timing of PB placement, recording the length of time it is left in place, when it is removed, and what position the PB was placed could potentially be operationalized and replicated in other studies. These efforts would offer increased reliability of the results and more trustworthy conclusions about the PBs effect on labor outcomes.

The potential benefits of this project are both short and long term. This project can instill and sustain confidence and a greater sense of agency in the nurse when evaluating and initiating pragmatic labor therapies. Therefore, nursing skills, knowledge, and PB use may increase after the instruction course and with poster reminders in the unit. As an intervention known to support and promote vaginal delivery, use of the PB may decrease the primary CS rate and improve maternal birth outcomes while reducing patient care costs.

Exciting opportunities have arisen from the pandemic circumstances that forced this project to be suspended. One is the invitation from two outside facilities that have requested the author act as a consultant on using the PB for their nursing staff.s The other is the ongoing discussions of the importance of PB use, CLS, and nurse-led quality improvement projects to decrease the NTSV CS rate at the project site. The use of the PB alone is not the whole solution to successful vaginal births, but this project is a reminder that nursing care and nursing-initiated interventions play a vital role in promoting healthy patient outcomes in the field of obstetrics.

References

- Altman, S. H., Butler, A. S., Shern, L., Committee for Assessing Progress on Implementing the Recommendations of the Institute of Medicine Report *The Future of Nursing: Leading Change, Advancing Health*, Institute of Medicine, & National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (Eds.). (2016). *Assessing progress on the institute of medicine report the future of nursing*. National Academies Press.
- Alton, S., Machamer, J., Shippen, C., Mayzel, M., & Grau, D. (2012). Improving labor support for patients in an urban, academic medical center: An evidence-based practice project. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic & Neonatal Nursing*, *41*(S1), S12. https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1552-6909.2012.01359_9.x
- American Academy of Pediatrics Committee on Fetus and Newborn (2012). Levels of neonatal care. *Pediatrics*, *130*(3), 587–597. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2012-1999>
- American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists, Society for Maternal-Fetal Medicine, Caughey, A. B., Cahill, A. G., Guise, J. M., & Rouse, D. J. (2014). Safe prevention of the primary cesarean delivery. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, *210*(3), 179–193. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajog.2014.01.026>
- American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists. (2019, February). ACOG committee opinion no. 766: Approaches to limit intervention during labor and birth. *Obstetrics and Gynecology*, *133*(2), e164–e173. <https://doi.org/10.1097/AOG.0000000000003074>
- American Nurses Association. (2015, July 21). *Organization for associate degree nursing and American Nurses Association joint position statement on academic progression to meet the needs of the registered nurse, the healthcare consumer, and the U.S. healthcare system*. <https://www.nursingworld.org/~490461/globalassets/practiceandpolicy/nursing->

[excellence/ana-position-statements/nursing-practice/academic-progression-ana-and-oadn-joint-position-statement-07-27-2015.pdf](#)

American Nursing Credentialing Center (n.d.). *Facts about the magnet recognition program.*

<https://www.nursingworld.org/~4b0951/globalassets/organizational-programs/magne/magnet-factsheet.pdf>

Anim-Somuah, M., Smyth, R. M., Cyna, A. M., & Cuthbert, A. (2018). Epidural versus non-epidural or no analgesia for pain management in labour. *Cochrane Database of*

Systematic Reviews, 5(5), CD000331. <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD000331.pub4>

Association of Women's Health, Obstetric & Neonatal Nursing (2011). Guidelines for professional registered nurse staffing for perinatal units executive summary. *Nursing for*

Women's Health, 15(1), 81–84. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-486X.2011.01603.x>

Association of Women's Health, Obstetric and Neonatal Nurses (2018). Continuous labor

support for every woman. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic, and Neonatal Nursing*, 47(1), 73–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jogn.2017.11.010>

Association of Women's Health, Obstetric and Neonatal Nursing. (2019). Basic, high-risk, and critical care intrapartum nursing: Clinical competencies and education guide, 6th edition.

Nursing for Women's Health, 23(2), E1-E22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nwh.2019.02.004>

Bawa, A. (2020, March 29). *Zoom's privacy policy*. <https://blog.zoom.us/zoom-privacy-policy/>

Bell, A. D., Joy, S., Gullo, S., Higgins, R., & Stevenson, E. (2017). Implementing a systematic approach to reduce cesarean birth rates in nulliparous women. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*,

130(5), 1082-1089. <https://doi.org/10.1097/AOG.0000000000002263>

Betran, A. P., Torloni, M. R., Zhang, J. J., Gülmezoglu, A. M., & WHO Working Group on

Caesarean Section (2016). WHO Statement on Caesarean Section Rates. *International*

- Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology*, 123(5), 667–670. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1471-0528.13526>
- Bohren, M. A., Hofmeyr, G. J., Sakala, C., Fukuzawa, R. K., & Cuthbert, A. (2017). Continuous support for women during childbirth. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, (7). <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD003766.pub6>
- Bréart, G., Mlika-Cabane, N., Kaminski, M., Alexander, S., Herruzo-Nalda, A., Mandruzzato, P., Thornton, J. G., & Trakas, D. (1992). Evaluation of different policies for the management of labour. *Early Human Development*, 29(1-3), 309–312. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-3782\(92\)90183-h](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-3782(92)90183-h)
- Brassard, M., & Ritter, D. (2010). *The memory jogger 2: Tools for continuous improvement and effective planning*. GOAL/QPC.
- Burke, C. (2013). Pain in labor: Nonpharmacologic and pharmacologic management. In K. R. Simpson, and P. A. Creehan (Eds.), *AWHONN's Perinatal Nursing* (pp. 493–527). Wolters Kluwer Health.
- California Maternal Quality Care Collaborative. (2018, April 23). *Appendix G: Guide to second stage management of malposition*. <https://www.cmqcc.org/resource/appendix-g-guide-second-stage-management-malposition>
- Campbell, D. A., Lake, M. F., Falk, M., & Backstrand, J. R. (2006). A randomized control trial of continuous support in labor by a lay doula. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic, and Neonatal Nursing*, 35(4), 456–464. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1552-6909.2006.00067.x>
- Committee on Quality of Health Care in America, & Institute of Medicine Staff. (2001). *Crossing the quality chasm: A new health system for the 21st century*. National Academies Press. <https://ebookcentral.proquest.com>

- Davies, B. L., & Hodnett, E. (2002). Labor support: nurses' self-efficacy and views about factors influencing implementation. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic, and Neonatal Nursing*, 31(1), 48–56. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1552-6909.2002.tb00022.x>
- Dickinson, J. E., Paech, M. J., McDonald, S. J., & Evans, S. F. (2002). The impact of intrapartum analgesia on labour and delivery outcomes in nulliparous women. *Australian & New Zealand Journal of Obstetrics & Gynaecology*, 42(1), 59–66. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0004-8666.2002.00065.x>
- Doulas of North America (n.d.). *What is a doula?* <http://dona.org/what-is-a-doula/>
- Djukic, M., Stimpfel, A. W., & Kovner, C. (2019). Bachelor's degree nurse graduates report better quality and safety educational preparedness than associate degree graduates. *Joint Commission Journal on Quality and Patient Safety*, 45(3), 180–186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcjq.2018.08.008>
- Edmonds, J. K., & Jones, E. J. (2013). Intrapartum nurses' perceived influence on delivery mode decisions and outcomes. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic, and Neonatal Nursing*, 42(1), 3–11. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1552-6909.2012.01422.x>
- Edmonds, J. K., O'Hara, M., Clarke, S. P., & Shah, N. T. (2017). Variation in cesarean birth rates by labor and delivery nurses. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic, and Neonatal Nursing*, 46(4), 486–493. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jogn.2017.03.009>
- Evans, S. J., & Cremering, M. M. (2016). Use of peanut labor ball for pelvic positioning for nulliparous women following epidural anesthesia. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic & Neonatal Nursing*, 45(3), S47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jogn.2016.03.119>

- Flynn, R., Scott, S. D., Rotter, T., & Hartfield, D. (2017). The potential for nurses to contribute to and lead improvement science in health care. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 73(1), 97–107. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.13164>
- Gagnon, A. J., Waghorn, K., & Covell, C. (1997). A randomized trial of one-to-one nurse support of women in labor. *Birth*, 24(2), 71-77.
- Gale, J., Fothergill-Bourbonnais, F., & Chamberlain, M. (2001). Measuring nursing support during childbirth. *American Journal of Maternal Child Nursing*, 26(5), 264–271. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00005721-200109000-00010>
- Gitlin, J. (n.d.). *How we protect your survey data and 3 steps you can take to keep it safe*. <https://www.surveymonkey.com/curiosity/how-we-protect-your-survey-data-and-3-steps-you-can-take-to-keep-it-safe/>
- Gregory, K. D., Jackson, S., Korst, L., & Fridman, M. (2012). Cesarean versus vaginal delivery: Whose risks? Whose benefits?. *American Journal of Perinatology*, 29(1), 7–18. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0031-1285829>
- Grenvik, J. M., Rosenthal, E., Saccone, G., Della Corte, L., Quist-Nelson, J., Gerkin, R. D., Gimovsky, A. C., Kwan, M., Mercier, R., & Berghella, V. (2019). Peanut ball for decreasing length of labor: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *European Journal of Obstetrics, Gynecology, and Reproductive Biology*, 242, 159–165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejogrb.2019.09.018>
- Grove, S. K., & Gray, J.R. (2019). *Understanding nursing research: Building an evidence – based practice* (7th ed.). Elsevier/Saunders.
- Hasegawa, J., Farina, A., Turchi, G., Hasegawa, Y., Zanello, M., & Baroncini, S. (2013). Effects of epidural analgesia on labor length, instrumental delivery, and neonatal short-term

outcome. *Journal of Anesthesia*, 27(1), 43–47. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00540-012-1480-9>

Hemminki, E., Virta, A. L., Koponen, P., Malim, M., Kojo-Austin, H., & Tuimala, R. (1990). A trial on continuous human support during labor: feasibility, interventions and mothers' satisfaction. *Journal of Psychosomatic Obstetrics & Gynecology*, 11(4), 239-250.

Hickey, L., & Savage, J. (2019). Effect of peanut ball and position changes in women laboring with an epidural. *Nursing for Women's Health*, 23(3), 245–252.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nwh.2019.04.004>

Hodnett, E. D., Lowe, N. K., Hannah, M. E., Willan, A. R., Stevens, B., Weston, J. A., Ohlsson, A., Gafni, A., Muir, H. A., Myhr, T. L., Stremler, R., and Nursing Supportive Care in Labor Trial Group (2002). Effectiveness of nurses as providers of birth labor support in North American hospitals: A randomized controlled trial. *Journal of the American Medical Association*, 288(11), 1373–1381. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.288.11.1373>

Huynh, L., McCoy, M., Law, A., Tran, K. N., Knuth, S., Lefebvre, P., Sullivan, S., Duh, M. S. (2013). Systematic literature review of the costs of pregnancy in the US. *Pharmacoeconomics*, 31(11), 1005-30. <https://search-proquest-com.lib-proxy.fullerton.edu/docview/1495405684?accountid=9840>

Institute for Healthcare Improvement. (n.d). *Science of improvement: Establishing measures*.
<http://www.ihl.org/resources/Pages/HowtoImprove/ScienceofImprovementEstablishingMeasures.aspx>

Institute for Healthcare Improvement. (n.d.b). *Science of improvement: Selecting changes*.
<http://www.ihl.org/resources/Pages/HowtoImprove/ScienceofImprovementSelectingChanges.aspx>

- Johnston, J. (1997). Birth balls. *Midwifery Today with International Midwife*, (43), 59-67.
- Kashanian, M., Javadi, F., & Haghghi, M. M. (2010). Effect of continuous support during labor on duration of labor and rate of cesarean delivery. *International Journal of Gynaecology and Obstetrics: The Official Organ of the International Federation of Gynaecology and Obstetrics*, 109(3), 198–200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijgo.2009.11.028>
- Lagrew, D. C., Kane Low, L., Brennan, R., Corry, M. P., Edmonds, J. K., Gilpin, B. G., Frost, J., Pinger, W., Reisner, D. P., & Jaffer, S. (2018). National partnership for maternal safety: consensus bundle on safe reduction of primary cesarean births-supporting intended vaginal births. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic, and Neonatal Nursing*, 47(2), 214–226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jogn.2018.01.008>
- Liao, J. B., Buhimschi, C. S., & Norwitz, E. R. (2005). Normal labor: Mechanism and duration. *Obstetrics and Gynecology Clinics of North America*, 32(2), 145–vii. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ogc.2005.01.001>
- Langley, G. J., Nolan, K. M., & Nolan, T. W. (1994). The foundation of improvement. *Quality Progress*, 27(6), 81-86.
- Langley, G. J., Moen, R. D., Nolan, K. M., Nolan, T. W., Norman, C. L., & Provost, L. P. (2009). *The improvement guide: A practical approach to enhancing organizational performance*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Lawrence, A., Lewis, L., Hofmeyr, G. J., & Styles, C. (2013). Maternal positions and mobility during first stage labour. *The Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, (10), CD003934. <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD003934.pub4>

Lloyd, R. (n.d.a). *Institute for healthcare improvement: Open school: Static vs dynamic data.*

<http://www.ihl.org/education/IHIOpenSchool/resources/Pages/AudioandVideo/Whiteboard10.aspx>

Lloyd, R. (n.d.b). *Institute for healthcare improvement: Open school: Control charts (part 1).*

<http://www.ihl.org/education/IHIOpenSchool/resources/Pages/AudioandVideo/Whiteboard13.aspx>

Lloyd, R. (n.d.c). *Institute for healthcare improvement: Open school: Control charts (part 2).*

<http://www.ihl.org/education/IHIOpenSchool/resources/Pages/AudioandVideo/Whiteboard14.aspx>

Logan, L., & Stettler, S. (2019). Reduction of primary cesarean birth rate in a rural hospital driven by nurse-initiated peanut ball use in active labor. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic & Neonatal Nursing*, 48(3), S110.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jogn.2019.04.185>

Lythogue, A.D. (2014, April 7). *Peanut balls for labor - a valuable tool for promoting progress?*

<https://www.lamaze.org/Connecting-the-Dots/peanut-balls-for-labor-a-valuable-tool-for-promoting-progress>

Martin, J.A., Hamilton, B.E., Osterman, M.J.K., Driscoll, A.K., (2019). *Births: Final data for 2018. National Vital Statistics Reports*, 68(3). Hyattsville, MD: National Center for Health Statistics. 2019 National Vital Statistics.

https://www.cdc.gov/nchs/data/nvsr/nvsr68/nvsr68_13-508.pdf

MacDorman, M. F., & Declercq, E. (2019). Trends and state variations in out-of-hospital births in the United States, 2004-2017. *Birth*, 46(2), 279–288. <https://doi.org/10.1111/birt.12411>

- Mercier, R. J., & Kwan, M. (2018). Impact of peanut ball device on the duration of active labor: A randomized control trial. *American Journal of Perinatology*, 35(10), 1006-1011.
<https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0038-1636531>
- Miltner R. S. (2002). More than support: nursing interventions provided to women in labor. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic, and Neonatal Nursing*, 31(6), 753–761.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0884217502239214>
- Moen, R. D., Nolan, T. W., & Provost, L. P. (1991). *Improving quality through planned experimentation*. McGraw-Hill College.
- Moen, R. (2009, September). Foundation and History of the PDSA Cycle. In *Asian network for quality conference*. Tokyo.
https://www.deming.org/sites/default/files/pdf/2015/PDSA_History_Ron_Moen.pdf
- Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report (1993). *Rates of cesarean delivery-United States, 1991*.
<https://www.cdc.gov/mmwr/preview/mmwrhtml/00020285.htm>
- Murn N. L. (2019). Mothering the mother: An educational program for nurse-provided continuous labor support. *Journal of Perinatal Education*, 28(4), 199–209.
<https://doi.org/10.1891/1058-1243.28.4.199>
- Online - Utility.org (n.d.). *Tests document readability index*. https://www.online-utility.org/english/readability_test_and_improve.jsp
- Payant, L., Davies, B., Graham, I. D., Peterson, W. E., & Clinch, J. (2008). Nurses' intentions to provide continuous labor support to women. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic & Neonatal Nursing*, 37(4), 405-414. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1552-6909.2008.00257.x>
- Polit, D.F. (2010). *Statistics and data analysis for nursing research* (2nd ed.). Pearson Education Inc.

- Polit, D. F., & Beck, C. T. (2008). *Nursing research: Generating and assessing evidence for nursing practice*. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
- Pryor, M. G. (2006). Quality Gurus. In M. M. Helms (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of Management* (5th ed., pp. 725-735). Gale. https://link-gale-com.lib.proxy.fullerton.edu/apps/doc/CX3446300244/GVRL?u=csuf_main&sid=GVRL&xid=3c5157bb
- Provost, L., & Murray, S. (2011). *The health care data guide: Learning from data for improvement* (1st ed.). Jossey-Bass.
- Prybutok G. L. (2018). Ninety to nothing: A PDSA quality improvement project. *International Journal of Health Care Quality Assurance*, 31(4), 361–372.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/IJHCQA-06-2017-0093>
- Roberts, L., Gulliver, B., Fisher, J., & Cloyes, K. G. (2010). The coping with labor algorithm: An alternate pain assessment tool for the laboring woman. *Journal of Midwifery & Women's Health*, 55(2), 107–116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmwh.2009.11.002>
- Roth, C., Dent, S. A., Parfitt, S. E., Hering, S. L., & Bay, R. C. (2016). Randomized controlled trial of use of the peanut ball during labor. *American Journal of Maternal/Child Nursing*, 41(3), 140-146. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NMC.0000000000000240>
- Sauls, D. (2002). Effects of labor support on mothers, babies, and birth outcomes. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic, and Neonatal Nursing*, 31(6), 733-741.
<http://doi.org/10.1177/0884217502239209>
- Shafer, L., & Aziz, M. G. (2013). Shaping a unit's culture through effective nurse-led quality improvement. *Medsurg Nursing*, 22(4), 229–236.

- Simkin, P., & Bolding, A. (2004). Update on nonpharmacologic approaches to relieve labor pain and prevent suffering. *Journal of Midwifery & Women's Health*, 49(6), 489–504.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmwh.2004.07.007>
- Simpson, K. R., Lyndon, A., Spetz, J., Gay, C. L., & Landstrom, G. L. (2019). Adherence to the AWHONN Staffing Guidelines as Perceived by Labor Nurses. *Nursing for Women's Health*, 23(3), 217–223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nwh.2019.03.003>
- Smith, H., Peterson, N., Lagrew, D., & Main, E. (2016). Toolkit to support vaginal birth and reduce primary cesareans: A quality improvement toolkit [PDF File]. *California Maternal Quality Care Collaborative*. <http://www.cmqcc.org>.
- Torrance, J. (2020, December 4). *Jessica Torrance, CNM, DNP student Peanut Ball Educational Video* [Video]. Vimeo. <https://vimeo.com/487380962/7225289088>
- Truven Health Analytics Marketscan Study. (2013, January). *The cost of having a baby in the United States*. <http://nationalpartnership.org/our-work/resources/health-care/maternity/archive/the-cost-of-having-a-baby-in-the-us.pdf>
- Tussey, C. M., Botsios, E., Gerkin, R. D., Kelly, L. A., Gamez, J., & Mensik, J. (2015). Reducing length of labor and cesarean surgery rate using a peanut ball for women laboring with an epidural. *Journal of Perinatal Education*, 24(1), 16.
<https://doi.org/10.18911058-1243.24.1.16>
- United States Census Bureau. (n.d.). *Quick facts, Irvine city, CA: Population estimates as of July 2019*. <https://www.census.gov/quickfacts/fact/table/irvinecitycalifornia/PST045218 - PST045218>.
- Weiss, E.R. & Levine, B. (2019, October 23). *Fetal positions for labor and birth*. <https://www.verywellfamily.com/fetal-positions-for-labor-and-birth-2759020>.

Zwelling E. (2008). The emergence of high-tech birthing. *Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic, and Neonatal Nursing*, 37(1), 85–93. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1552-6909.2007.00211.x>

Zwelling E. (2010). Overcoming the challenges: maternal movement and positioning to facilitate labor progress. *The American Journal of Maternal Child Nursing*, 35(2), 72–80. <https://doi-org.lib-proxy.fullerton.edu/10.1097/NMC.0b013e3181caeab3>

Appendix A

Survey Informational Sheet

Title of Project: Improving Peanut Ball Use: A Quality Improvement Project Survey

Investigator: Jessica M.. Torrance, CNM, DNP student.

Telephone: redacted

You are being asked to be in a voluntary Doctorate of Nursing (DNP) project regarding the peanut ball device used by nurses while caring for nulliparous, term, singleton, vertex (NTSV) laboring patients.

You are being asked to take part in this research because you are an adult over age 18 and a registered nurse on the labor and delivery unit. This information seeks to help understand the nurses' knowledge of peanut ball devices. Your decision to be in this study is completely voluntary.

Purpose

The objectives of this study are to increase the utilization of the peanut ball device in NTSV laboring patients and to reduce labor hours by implementing a video instructional course and poster display on the intrapartum unit.

Duration

If you decide to participate, I will be asking you a series of questions about the peanut ball device that will take about 3-5 minutes to complete.

Voluntary participation

You do not have to answer any questions that you do not want to answer. The questions you answer as part of this research project are used for research purposes only.

Study procedure

Prior to the peanut ball instructional video course, a pre-project survey will be emailed to you to your work email address from SurveyMonkey™. After the project is completed, you will be emailed a post-project survey from SurveyMonkey™. The survey will examine knowledge of the peanut ball device and will also evaluate individual knowledge improvement after the project is completed.

Risks

There are minimal risks to participants in this study. You can refuse to answer or skip any questions. The main risk is a loss of confidentiality.

Benefits/Alternatives

There is no guarantee that you will benefit from participating in this study. You do not have to participate in this study.

Confidentiality

To maintain your confidentiality, all email addresses used will not be shared per the SurveyMonkey™ privacy rules and regulations. Only the author, Jessica Torrance, will have access to the data on the survey site. Passwords will not be shared. After project completion and survey analysis, all access will be halted and any personal information (email addresses) destroyed. The results will never be presented so that you can be identified.

Compensation/Costs

You will not be paid for participating in this study. There are no costs to you for participating in this research study.

Contact information

If you have any questions about this research study, please call Jessica Torrance.

Appendix B
Project Survey Form

Age:

Years of Nursing:

Highest Nursing Degree Achieved (circle one) ADN, BSN, MSN, PhD, DNP

Survey:

- 1) In some cases, peanut ball devices are useful to decrease the length of labor in NTSV (nulliparous, term, singleton, vertex) patients? True or False or I don't know (True)
- 2) Peanut balls can impact the rate of CS in NTSV patients? True or False or I don't know (True)
- 3) Peanut balls have been well studied in research? True or False or I don't know (False)
- 4) If a baby's position is the right occiput posterior (ROP), what is the best side for the patient to be placed upon after the Peanut Ball is set in place to assist with rotation to an occiput posterior (OA) position? Right or Left (Right) (CMQCC, 2018).

Appendix C

Class Outline for PB Educational Video

- I. Introduction
- II. Overview of studies - Ongoing studies being done. Not much published. Meta-analysis of four randomized control trials done by Grenvik et al. (2019) decreased risk of CS for NTSV patients. A quasi-experimental study compared current PB users to similar non-PB users in the past revealed no difference in the first stage of labor, but a decreased risk of CS in PB users (Hickey & Savage, 2019). Two RCTs demonstrated decreased 1st stage of labor (Tussey et al., 2015; Roth et al., 2016).
- III. Review peanut balls (PB)s available on the unit (PB size depending on height and comfort of patient). Contraindicated in patients with hip/pelvic injuries. Importance of following protocol for turning and moving patient (Smith et al., 2016).
 - a. Demonstrate in conjunction with the poster side lying-PB between upper thighs, knees and ankles parallel.
 - b. Demonstrate in conjunction with the poster side lying in a semi-prone position. Upper knee hooked on the smaller portion of PB. Ideal for ROP babies (CMQCC, 2018; Lythogue, 2014).
- V. Remind staff to use PB consistently on appropriate patients and chart when PB is placed.
- VI. Review of inflation and deflation of PB.

References available on request

Appendix D

Project Poster

Side Lying Position

Right Side Lying Semi-Prone (best for ROP presentation)

Appendix E

Project Flow Chart Poster

*Note.*Flow chart (below) will also be printed on posters

Appendix F

Peanut Ball Use Run Chart

